

FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF TOBACCO SEED OIL

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The oil from Virginia tobacco seeds of Guntur District (Madras) has been examined and the fatty acid composition determined. Mixed fatty acids consist of myristic (1.8%), palmitic (7.8%), stearic (5.6%), oleic (30.2%) and linoleic (54.6%). The oil contains 1.9% non-saponifiable matter which is mainly sitosterol (w.p. 141*).

Tobacco plant belongs to the natural order *Solanaceae* and to the genus *Nicotiana*, subdivided into the species *Nicotiana rustica* and *Nicotiana tobacum*. The present investigation deals with the seed oil of Virginia tobacco belonging to the species *Nicotiana tobacum*. The total acreage under tobacco cultivation in the Madras Presidency for the year 1941-42 was about 334,000 acres out of which Virginia variety occupied 129,000 acres. Out of this, Guntur district alone contributed 87,000 acres (Madras Agrl. Dept. personal communication), the average yield of seed per acre from the Virginia variety being about 175 lbs. The total production of seed in this district works out to be 6800 tons which on solvent extraction would give about 2000 tons of oil and 4800 tons of seed cake.

The oil from the seeds has been investigated by several workers and its particular property of drying has also been studied. In Guntur district, which stands foremost in tobacco cultivation in South India, the seeds are not utilised for any useful purpose except as cattle fodder, firstly because of the difficulty of extracting the oil and secondly due to lack of proper initiative in the utilisation of the oil. In other countries the oil is recommended for edible purposes and also as a drying oil (Brambilla and Balbi, *Chim. et Ind.*, 1938, 20, 548).

In view of the importance of tobacco cultivation in this district, great prominence is attached to the profitable utilisation of the seed which will add to the material benefit of the farmer. With this view the indigenous oil has been subjected to a thorough chemical investigation and the fatty acid composition and glyceride structure determined as a prelude to its ultimate commercial exploitation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fresh seeds of Virginia tobacco grown in the district were collected in March 1943 and the oil was extracted with carbon tetrachloride after thoroughly grinding the seed in a buhr-stone. The yield of the oil is 28%. The analytical figures of the oil along with those of the previous workers in other countries are given in Table I.

Fatty Acid Composition

200 G. of the oil were saponified with alcoholic soda and the non-saponifiables removed by extracting the soap with ether after thoroughly mixing it with asbestos. The fatty acids were liberated and subjected to Twitchell's lead salt-alcohol and other method of separation (Twitchell, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806). The fatty acid portions obtained from lead-salts soluble in alcohol (A) and in ether (E) were converted into their respective methyl esters and fractionated at 0.2 mm. pressure. The fatty acids from the insoluble lead salts (S) were separated by fractional crystallisation of their barium salts by Heintz method, as the quantity was small for fractionation.

TABLE I

Constants.	Present workers.*	Greek tobacco seed oil.	Philippine oil (Cruz & West).	Moroco & Gracilin.	Belary.	Rao & Anjan-yah.
Sp. gr.	0.9405 at 35.3°	at 20° 0.9440 0.9253	at 30° 0.9130	0.9259	0.9254	0.9254 at 16°
Ref. index	1.460 at 37°	at 25° 1.4735 1.4828	at 30° 1.4774	1.4756		
Acid. val.	0.7024	2.25 to 16.93	16.8	2.57	9	
Iodine val.	112.2	117.8 117.9	135.8	135.46	135.34	142
Sap. val.	191.2	186.8	190.5	194.6	200.7	
Non sap. %	2.0	—	1.41	1.53	—	
Hehner val.	93	96.21 to 96.3	—	—	—	

TABLE II

	Wt.	Sap. equiv.	I. Val.
Oil	200 g.	293.4	112.2
Mixed acids	182 g.	237.7	120.6
EtOH soluble acids (A)	56 g.	278.6	144.4
Ether soluble acids (B)	97.5 g.	267.9	126.8
Alcohol soluble acids (S)	28.5 g.	277.7	54.40
Esters (A)	—	294.9	139.2
Esters (B)	—	285.6	127.6

* Due to the freshness of the seed and its immediate extraction with carbon tetrachloride the present sample has a low acid value (0.7% as oleic acid). It is also characterised by a lower iodine value probably due to the climatic conditions.

TABLE III

Esters (A)

Fr. No.	Temp.	Fr. wt.	Sap. equiv.	I. V.	Identifications.	Fractions at
1	110-50°	4.8 g.	286.1	126.1	M, P, O, L.	112-45°
2	150-55°	10.2	291.3	143.7	P. O., & L.	145-46°
3	156-59°	9.4	294.3	150.9	O & L.	146-52°
4	159-61°	19.0	294.4	150	— —	Residue
5	Residue.	14.6	295.2 (corr.)	120.9	— —	

TABLE IV

Esters (B)

Fr. wt.	Sap. equiv.	I. V.	Identifications
5.4 g.	278.7	122.4	M, O & L.
24.2	292.8	142.9	P, O & L.
3.8	290.0	137.9	P, O & L.
9.4	291.8	103.6	— —

M = Myristic; O = Oleic; P = Palmitic; L = Linoleic.

TABLE V

Acids (S)

Fr. no.	Fr. wt.	Sap. equiv.	I. V.	M.p.	Identifications.
1	1.42 g.	276	0.96	53-54°	Palmitic and stearic
2	2.8	276.1	9.35	52-53°	Palmitic, stearic & Oleic
3	0.8	277.6	15.5	52-53°	— —
4	2.4	283.0	21.2	55-56°	— —
5	12.4	280.5	66.6	51-52°	— —

Among the saturated fatty acids myristic (m.p. 52°), palmitic (m.p. 62°) and stearic (m.p. 63°) acids were identified by finding out the mixed melting points with authentic samples. Oleic and linoleic acids were identified by alkaline permanganate oxidation (Lapworth and Mottram, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1628) when dihydroxystearic acid (m.p. 131°) and tetrahydroxy stearic acid (m.p. 170-71°) were obtained. Further, on brominating the mixed fatty acids tetrabromostearic acid (m.p. 114°) was obtained and no hexabromide could be detected. The percentage composition of the various acids has been calculated from the above fractions and given below along with the figures reported for Philippine, American and Russian oils.

TABLE IV

	Guntur sample.			Philippine.		American.		Russian.
	LA%	E.A.%	S.A.%	Total	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Myristic	30'70 0'20	53'60 1'60	15'70 —	100 1'8	0'05	—	—	—
Palmitic	0'90	4'20	1'70	7'8	7'25	3'3	9'8	10'5
Stearic	—	—	5'60	5'6	3'1	5'1	5'9	—
Arachidic	—	+	...	—	0'4	—	—	—
Oleic	9'10	13'70	7'40	30'2	27'1	17'1	28'0	23'8
Linoleic	20'50	34'1	—	54'6	62'1	74'5	56'5	65'7

The palmitic acid content of the oil, which is the characteristic saturated fatty acid of this group of oils, is 7.8 confirming the observation of Hilditch ('Oils, Fats and Waxes,' p. 11). In this respect it differs from kapok and cottonseed oils. Of all the samples reported in the above table Philippine oil alone contains arachidic acid and no trace of arachidic acid could be detected in the present sample.

Non-saponifiable Matter

The non-saponifiable matter consisted of beautiful shining crystalline needles which melted on crystallisation from methyl alcohol-acetone mixture (3:1) at 140-141° indicating the presence of sitosterol. Further on benzoylation it gave needles which on crystallisation from benzene-alcohol mixture (1:1) melted at 143°, confirming the presence of the above sterol.

The glyceride structure of the oil by the method of bromination of the neutral oil and separation of the bromoglycerides from various solvents is in progress.

(1) Cruz and West, *Phil. J. Sci.*, 1937, 81, 161.

(2) *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 58, 207.

(3) *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 117, 21.

(4) U. S. S. R. *State Inst. Tobacco Inv.*, Bul., 1929, 61, 20.